

Figure 2.

Factor	Effect
<p>Eating during Daylight vs Nighttime</p>	<p>Eating earlier in the day (during daylight):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improves body weight control • Improves glycemic control, ↓ postprandial Glu peak, • ↑ Postprandial insulin (secretion/sensitivity), ↑ GLP-1 • ↓ Diabetes risk • Improves hunger regulation (via aligning with normal daily oscillations of ghrelin)
<p>Carbohydrates</p>	<p>Less CHO in the meals/day and less readily available CHO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ↓ Postprandial glucose excursions • ↑ Insulin responses • ↓ Insulin resistance • Early consumption of CHO: ↓ postprandial glucose, insulin, GLP-1
<p>Protein/Fat Preload</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prolong gastric emptying • ↓ Absorption of CHO • ↓ Postprandial glucose • ↑ Insulin release • Improves β-cell function • ↑ GLP-1 • ↑ Satiety
<p>Fibers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ↓ Absorption of CHO • ↓ Gastric emptying • ↓ Postprandial glucose • ↑ Satiety • ↓ Risk for diabetes
<p>Slow vs Fast Eating</p>	<p>Fast eaters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weight gain, ↑ Postprandial glucose peaks, • ↑ Daily glycemic excursions <p>Slow eaters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced diet-induced thermogenesis, • ↑ Serum adiponectin, ↑ NEFA, • ↓ IL-1β/IL-6 and positive influence on ghrelin and PYY
<p>Exercise / Physical Activity</p>	<p>↓Postprandial glucose ↓Body weight ↓Fasting/Postprandial insulin ↓HOMA ↓HbA1c ↓Diabetes risk ↓TRiglycerides ↑IRS1 and GLUT1 mRNA ↑HDL</p>
<p>Spices, herbs, yogurt, vinegar, trace elements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ↓Diabetes risk • Trend towards improved glycemia (↑Insulin, ↓HbA1c, ↓postprandial hyperglycemia,) • Improved lipidemia (↓chol, ↓TG, ↓LDL, ↑ HDL) • ↓CHO intestinal absorption due to fat content • Delayed gastric emptying (vinegar) • Delayed digestion of CHO (vinegar) • Improved muscle glucose uptake (vinegar)